

An Investigation of The Dominant Themes In Online Political Leadership Campaigns: A Case Study Of The *OBIdient* Campaign Discourse on X

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Abstract

Background: The persuasive function of language is perhaps most evident in political campaigns. The Nigerian political context is expected to reflect a robust adaptation of persuasion. Therefore, the *OBIdient* movement, a new phenomenon in the Nigerian political space, would offer an engaging framework for evaluating the persuasive dynamics of political communication in Nigeria.

Objective: This study investigates the dominant themes in the *OBIdient* campaign discourse on X (formerly Twitter).

Methodology: This research used a descriptive qualitative research design. The data for this work were drawn from tweets from members of the *OBIdient* campaign movement. Dell Hymes' (1964) ethnography of communication (SPEAKING) was used to analyse the tweets from members of the *OBIdient* campaign movement. The ethnographic dimensions of the campaign necessitated the choice of this model.

Results: The findings of this study revealed the following dominant themes: persuasion, admiration, gratitude, religion/focus, transparency/good governance, hate politics, and political killing.

Unique Contribution: This work adds to the sparse literature available in this area and the use of Dell Hyme's Ethnography of Communication - SPEAKING model in doing a case study analysis of political discourse.

Conclusion: Social media platforms have changed the dynamics of political discourse globally and Nigeria is no exception.

Recommendation: Further studies may consider a comparison between data obtained from other social media platforms using a different theoretical framework. The researchers believe that suggested further studies would most likely widen the horizon of the impact of the *#Obidient* presidential campaign of 2023.

Keywords: *OBIdient* movement, Political Campaigns, SPEAKING, Ethnography of Communication, Online Political discourse.

Introduction

Language is indispensable in human communication. It is, therefore, a platform through which human beings express themselves in all spheres of human endeavour. Huma (2023) emphasises the compelling role of language, particularly evident in political campaigns. The Nigerian political landscape is anticipated to demonstrate a strong capacity for persuasion adaptation. Notably, substantial study exists in this field, albeit from the perspective of traditional media. Partington and Taylor (2018) delineate the relationship between mainstream media and political parties. They underscore language as a tool of influence and repeat that its substantial application in a democracy serves the purpose of persuasion in both mainstream and social media. Consequently, the utilisation of language is essential to the evolution of a nation's political framework.

Consequently, it is clear that language influences political activity and can alter public opinion; a significant factor that instigated a substantial shift in Nigeria's 2023 presidential election campaigns was the *OBIdient* movement. Despite the significant influence of the *OBIdient* movement, little action seems to have been taken. Despite several study initiatives concerning online political campaigns, there is a paucity of information regarding the 2023 presidential online political campaigns, particularly pertaining to the *OBIdient* movement. Limited progress has been made regarding the predominant themes of the movement. This serves as the principal impetus for this research. Online campaigns are a somewhat novel concept in Nigeria's social media environment. The *OBIdient* campaign movement has only recently begun to gain popularity among Nigerians on social media. Consequently, information regarding the *OBIdient* movement is limited. In light of the movement's growing support base, particularly in assessing the language employed by the *OBIdients*, an analysis of the prevailing themes in the *OBIdient* campaign discourse has become imperative.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the prevailing themes in online political campaigns, using the *OBIdient* Campaign discourse as a case study
2. To examine how the *OBIdient* campaign discourse was a political protest among the Youth.
3. To examine how the political discourse positioned the Youths as agents of change, thereby mobilising them to take action.

The Obidient Movement

Agbim et al. (2023) describe the *OBIdient* movement as a digital social campaign aimed at raising awareness across multiple media platforms for the political aspirations of Peter Obi, the Labour Party's presidential candidate in the 2023 general elections. It is the coalition of Nigerian youth and like-minded individuals aimed at achieving a democratic upheaval of the current regime in the 2023 presidential election. It can be considered a digital media product, typified by all digital communication associated with the Internet. Hussaini (2023) contends that the "*OBIdient*" movement seems to rejuvenate engagement in electoral politics among youth and may represent a counteractive force to the broader phenomenon of democratic lethargy. He characterises the *OBIdients* as technologically adept Nigerians. Regarding the *OBIdient* movement, Egbulefu et al. (2023) asserted that it is now indisputable that citizens are enduring excessive dissatisfaction due to the severely inadequate benefits of democracy resulting from the gross incompetence of various governmental administrations. Okwelum (2023), in his analysis of the *OBIdient* movement, attributed both its ascendancy and potential decline to the Nigerian youth.

Additionally, digital media is linked to the information revolution, which has propelled the developing multimedia landscape. Chimuanya and Igwebuikwe (2021) contend that social media are crucial platforms for widespread information distribution. As a result, this has led to the emergence of internet-based publications and citizen journalism, which have infiltrated many facets of society, including politics. This citizen journalism primarily uses social media sites like X, Facebook, and others. Oyewola et al. (2023) indicate that data from social media platforms, particularly from X, has been utilised for election monitoring and predictions. Igwebuikwe and Chimuanya (2023) utilised data from Facebook and X accounts to enhance their research.

Erubami (2020) asserts that social media tools have revolutionised global communication patterns. The "political tsunami" that followed the 2011/2012 Arab Spring (Ufuophu-Biri & Ojoboh, 2017) demonstrates that many authoritarian and autocratic regimes in certain African nations have been dismantled and supplanted by more democratic governments, facilitated by social media.

The Language of Political Discourse

Adegbija (1999:189) asserts that pragmatic analysis of language examines "the utilisation of language within specific communicative contexts or situations." In her study of Political Discourse, Pan (2019) contends that Pragmatics operates on various levels within the nexus of language, media, and politics. Jacobs et al. (2023) assert that political discourse is intricately intertwined with language, media, and politics, emphasising that politics is not isolated but engages dynamically with various institutional domains and actors, including news media, research organisations, non-governmental organisations, educational institutions, art entities, and businesses.

Edet et al. (2021) emphasise that language and linguistics constitute the foundation of any economy. Jacobs et al. (2023) utilise case studies on the discursive practices at the convergence of political science and journalism to illustrate that analysing the interaction among various institutional actors can reveal fundamental aspects of political discourse. Similarly, Farhat et al. (2018) assert that language empowers users, especially political figures, to articulate their political ideas and identities, leading these actors to manipulate such platforms to fulfil their established political objectives. Bozi (2023) asserts that individuals' linguistic selections may reflect their perceptions of tangible entities, rendering language a crucial medium for expressing their beliefs. Celjeta (2018) posits that the definition of politics would be broadened by releasing two seminal texts by Aristotle and Machiavelli, highlighting the essential attributes of politics: ethics and morality contrasted with hegemony and violence.

Theoretical Framework - Dell Hymes' Ethnography of Communication

Noy (2017) asserts that ethnography of communication (EC) is a multidisciplinary research methodology that utilises ethnographic narratives of actual communication events to understand communication's unique cultural and contextual aspects. EC is represented by the acronym SPEAKING, which comprises eight components: (1) S - Setting and Situation: The setting denotes the temporal and spatial context, whilst the situation delineates the surrounding circumstances. (2) P – Participants: This denotes the individuals engaged in the discourse, including the speaker and the listener. (3) E – Ends: This section addresses the purpose and objectives of the speech, along with its anticipated outcomes and aims. (4) A – Act / Sequence: This refers to the chronological

order of events throughout the speech. (5) K – Key refers to the speaker's attitude or demeanour. (6) I – Instrumentality: This refers to the structure and delivery of the speaker's discourse. (7) N – Norm delineates socially acceptable conduct during the event. (8) G – Genre pertains to the presented discourse type.

Materials and Methods

This research adopted a descriptive qualitative approach to analyse the data from tweets and retweets from the *OBIdients*. The tweets were selected to reflect the main themes of the tweets. The researchers adopted a purposive sampling technique to ensure a representative and structured data collection process. Tweets that were actively engaged in terms of high likes, comments, and retweets were chosen. The study also gathered data from verified associated *OBIdient* accounts, known figures, and some *OBIdient* movement members. The tweets were collected from before and after the 2023 presidential election period to capture the thematic trend. The data were collated using manual bookmarking and digital archiving. The original content was preserved through screenshots and text extraction to maintain accuracy.

Results and Discussions

In Dell Hymes' SPEAKING model, the G in SPEAKING denotes genre, signifying categorisation or classification. The principal themes in the piece are detailed below.

Theme 1 Persuasion

Tweet 1 - Peter Obi said 'Take back your country. This country belongs to YOU. It is YOUR FUTURE that they are toying with. You must TAKE IT BACK from them.

This succinct, impactful speech was delivered by Mr. Peter Obi, the presidential candidate of the Labour Party and the central figure of the *OBIdient* movement, but documented by a different source. Peter Obi said 'Take back your country. This country belongs to YOU. It is YOUR FUTURE that they are toying with. You must TAKE IT BACK from them.'

Here, Mr. Obi is encouraging the youths who form the more significant part of his prospective voters to take an active role in reclaiming their country from the old politicians who have plundered the nation and brought her to where she is today. He calls them out to seize the moment by getting involved in his attempt to wrestle power out of the hands of the older politicians. It is an identity expression emphasising that Nigeria belongs to the youths.

Again, by Obi's language, he urges the youths to be proactive in this election and not allow the same old people to manipulate or exploit their destiny. This theme often resonates with ideas of civic engagement, political responsibility, and a call to action. He is therefore advocating citizen involvement, particularly among the youth. The tweet's author emphasised specific segments of the speech indicating their significance. The parts foregrounded include YOU, YOUR FUTURE, and TAKE IT BACK.

Theme 2 - Admiration

Tweet 2 - Kenneth Okonkwo is GOATed. He single handedly bodied PDP and APC and APC's spokespersons again yesterday on Channels TV. Lol. I died when he said "everybody in APC is a thief including animals

The author admires Kenneth Okonkwo's rhetorical and political abilities. The term GOAT(ed) is a contemporary social media abbreviation signifying Greatest Of All Time. The author employed it as a verb in the past tense. This illustrates how the youth, X's primary users, have diminished the formality typically associated with the English language. The author hails Kenneth Okonkwo because of his deft ability to take on PDP and APC representatives on Channels television. He demonstrated his oratorical talents by adeptly navigating the session in the television studio. By labelling him as GOATed, the author evaluates him as superior to all other spokespersons on the panel. He is also happy that his party has a spokesperson who can take the other spokespersons to the cleaners anytime.

The author stated, 'he single-handedly bodied PDP and APC's spokespersons...' The author conveys his adoration for Okonkwo by employing the term 'bodied'. This parallels a football match, where a player employs physical force to displace an opponent to seize control of the ball and potentially score a goal. Kenneth Okonkwo is characterised as possessing an advantage in the discourse, so effectively representing his Party to the commendation of the *OBIdients*. 'I died when he said everybody in APC is a thief, including animals' Okonkwo illustrates the extent of corruption and moral decay within the APC. Animals are not human beings and, hence, cannot steal; thus, their inclusion in the list of thieves indicates alleged significant corruption within the APC. This is comprehensible as Okonkwo was a previous senior official of the APC. 'I died' signifies the author's profound horror upon discovering that even animals engage in thievery within the APC.

***Tweet 3** -For me, it's the way he smiles before answering a question. And when he smiles like that, just know wotowoto is around the corner*

We see the theme of admiration still running through this tweet. The author refers to Okonkwo's smile as the signal for a hit from him to his opponents. The author combined the extra-linguistic element of a smile and other linguistic elements to understand the direction Okonkwo is going. When he smiles before speaking, the author believes he is about to deal hard with his opponents. Okonkwo, a lawyer and a politician, has an apparent rhetorical ability. Wotowoto is a social media language meaning 'plenty' or 'much'.

***Tweet 4** - ...@realkenokonkwo is a king Kong in the forest of DRC Congo.*

The author likens Kenneth to King Kong, a mythical colossal gorilla in DRC Congo renowned for its power and supremacy. By likening Kenneth Okonkwo to a 'King Kong in the forest of DRC Congo,' the author depicts Okonkwo as a formidable figure in the television discourse.

***Tweet 5** – OKONKWO is a terror to the EMILOKANS hahahaaaaaa*

The author implies through this tweet that Okonkwo serves as a formidable presence for the other representatives. His rhetorical prowess intimidates, threatens, and overwhelms the other speakers. This metaphorical statement depicts Okonkwo as an individual who evokes terror among the EMILOKANS. The Emilokans are constituents of the APC and are affiliated with and supportive of Tinubu's party. Tinubu delivered a speech before the primaries in which he employed the term "emilokan." It is a Yoruba phrase signifying, 'It is my turn.' He asserted that it was his opportunity

to become the president of Nigeria. Since then, his party members have been referred to as EMILOKANS.

Tweet 6 – Kenneth is the Peter Drury of politics.

The author juxtaposes Kenneth with Peter Drury, a British sports pundit renowned for his adept use of the English language. His style is frequently poetic. This comparison reveals that Okonkwo embodies comparable attributes, and the author expresses satisfaction that the *OBIdients* have a representative to advocate for their agenda. The concept of admiration permeates all these tweets. Members of the *OBIdient* movement who viewed the conversation on Channels TV were impressed with their spokesperson, which reinvigorated their hope for the electoral success of their presidential candidate.

Tweet 7 – Zack as your head correct for film na so e correct for real life not some idiot yeyebriy

The author commends Zack Amata, a seasoned Nollywood actor and an *OBIdient* campaigner who advocates for the youth to recover their rightful land. The author compares Zack, the actor, with Zack, the politician, concluding that Zack exhibits wisdom both on and off the stage. He compared Zack to 'some idiot yeyebriy.' The term 'yeyebriy' is a neologism derived from the Yoruba word 'yeye,' signifying worthless, combined with the suffix of 'cele-briy.' The author mentioned additional celebrities who have allied with APC and PDP. He contends that celebrities are youthful individuals who need to join the *OBIdient* movement, which aims to reclaim their country from corrupt, ageing politicians.

Theme 3 - Gratitude

Tweet 8 – Zack Amata thank you for reminding the other youths 10k have blocked their ears. They don't know what is coming for them if they refuse to listen to the voice of wisdom

The author expresses gratitude to Zack Amata for reminding the youth of the advice given by Peter Obi. He asserts that the N10,000.00 bribe received from corrupt politicians obscures their awareness that reclaiming their country would be more advantageous. The author implies that the N10,000.00 distributed by corrupt politicians serves as a means to distract the youth, incentivising them to cast their votes in favour of these politicians. The funding may be contingent upon the candidate's financial capacity. One of the slogans of the *OBIdients* is 'we no dey give shishi,' signifying their refusal to buy votes or financially incentivise voters to support their preferred politicians.

Theme 4 - Religion/Focus

Tweet 9 – Dear Nigeria youths, don't get distracted with Governor Soludo's endorsement of Atiku Abubakar. You can achieve your aim without the support of any Governor. Take charge of your struggle and result will be yours. I encourage you to be focused. We are praying for you.

The author urges the youth to be focused and determined to reclaim the nation from ineffective politicians. He saw Governor XYZ's backing of Atiku Abubakar as a diversion and urged them to remain undeterred. He informed them that their perseverance would ultimately yield results. He said that we, the nation, were praying for them. This religious angle means so much to the *OBIdients* as Nigerians in general are known to be religious people.

Tweet 10 –Your Eminence, we appreciate your fatherly counsel. We don't care about XYZ. He can endorse Satan if he wishes. He has just one vote for his Atiku. He cannot influence anyone else but himself. Thank you Servant of God

The author expresses gratitude to the servant of God for advising them to remain undistracted by XYZ's endorsement of Atiku. The phrase 'he can endorse Satan if he wishes' is a clear indication that the battle line is drawn between the two parties, the Labour Party and the PDP. It shows the parallel line between the *OBIdents' candidate, who is often seen as a symbol of uprightness*, and the other candidates. Again, it shows that the *OBIdents* believe they are sure of victory and cannot be distracted by any opposition. It further shows the resolve and commitment of the *OBIdents* on their chosen course to ensure that they vote for their preferred candidate, Mr Peter Obi.

Tweet 11 – *Pharaoh did more than this but still ended up sinking in the waters. By the time they will discover God is involved with Peter, it would be too late.*

This tweet shows the author's resolute support for Peter Obi. He likens the old politicians in Nigeria who have refused to relinquish power to the younger people to Pharaoh who enslaved the Israelites for four hundred and thirty years. By using the phrase, 'ended up sinking in the waters', the author believes Peter Obi's opponents will suffer the same fate. His second sentence, 'By the time they will discover God is involved with Peter, it would be too late' portrays Peter Obi as a chosen leader. This religious approach to a political issue strengthens the resolve of the *OBIdents* to ensure that they vote their candidate into power.

Tweet 12 - *Craw go meet him for night as per necodemos*

The author addresses the claim made by APC supporters that Obasanjo's endorsement of Peter Obi holds no value. S/he counsels them to approach Obasanjo at night, as they would be embarrassed to encounter him during the day. Necodemos refers to Nicodemus, the tax collector in the Bible (John 3: 1-21) who visited Jesus at night due to apprehension of the potential repercussions from his relatives, the Pharisees if he were to go during the day. The author misspelt "crawl" as "craw." This error or omission may be intentional. The X language is characterised by spontaneity. X users communicate spontaneously and consequently employ abbreviations. They often abbreviate their statements due to the restricted space on the X platform. More often, they want to be the first to publish any trending news, and errors occur in that rush. Such errors may also come from interference with the mother tongue.

Tweet 13 – *And Tinubu refused to wash his hands for several hours following a handshake with OBJ. That handshake was like anointing to him.*

This *OBIdient* derides APC supporters who claim that Obasanjo's (OBJ) backing of Peter Obi is insignificant. He compares the handshake between Obasanjo and ABC to an anointing that destroys the yoke as stated in Isaiah 10:27. This signifies that every yoke associated with ABC would be broken by the anointing derived from the handshake.

Tweet 14 – *The best endorsement for Peter Obi of the Labour party in this coming Election is God Endorsement...*

The author suggests the omnipotence of God and asserts that His support for Obi exceeds that of any individual, including XYZ.

Tweet 15 – *If u are a youth if obj letters no give una concern, I pity ur future, obj don do him own he is at peace dey wait for God call, make una sell una future and that of ur generation own join he who has ears let him hear what the Spirit is saying*

The author cautions the youth to follow Obasanjo's counsel to unite and effectuate significant change, as their future and that of the nation rests in their hands. He asserts that Obasanjo has completed his endeavours and, as an elderly individual, he is at peace with God, awaiting death and entry into heaven, unlike the Youth who still have enough time to shape their future. He closes by exhorting the youth to heed the messages of the Holy Spirit. This is based on Revelation 2:29 and Revelation 3:22.

Tweet 16 – *Hello tweeps, I suggest aside 4rm rooting @Peter Obi, we should put him in serious prayers for divine protection & God shd use him 2 indeed move Nigeria 4ward with good hearted people 2 work with him' our expectations must indeed not be in vain. God will help us succeed dis 2023.*

This tweet strongly showcases the theme of religion as seen in the phrase, 'serious prayers for divine protection'. This portrays the author's belief in divine guardianship. The author further used the phrase, 'God shd use him to move Nigeria 4ward', portraying Peter Obi as a messiah who has come to deliver his people. This elicits hope that Nigeria is on the road to recovery. Finally, the phrase, 'God will help us succeed,' reawakens the author's hope in our collective resolve to see a Nigeria where there is freedom, peace, and unity.

Tweet 17 – *Everything works together for good to us who believe in the liberation of Nigeria through Peter Obi. The more they punish Nigerians because of Peter Obi, the more Nigerians are loving him and collecting their PVC to vote for Peter Obi.*

The author adopts a spiritual perspective by referencing Romans 8:28, which states that all things work for the good of those who love God. This scripture from the author's perspective points to the fact that there is hope for Nigeria if Peter Obi, the *OBI*dients' candidate, is voted in. By that scripture, the author believes that the *OBI*dients have the assurance of victory. The phrase, 'us who believe in the liberation of Nigeria through Peter Obi' shows the author's avowed belief in Obi as the Deliverer God appointed for Nigeria. The last sentence, 'The more they punish Nigerians because of Peter Obi, the more Nigerians are loving him and collecting their PVC to vote for Peter Obi' shows the futility of the antagonism from the opposition and the frustration felt by Nigerians because rather than deter them, it serves as a motivating factor to vote their candidate in.

Tweet 18 – *I am a 56 year old Yoruba man from Ekiti. My entire family and I will be voting for Peter Obi, any member of my family that vote Tinubu will be eternally cursed. No sane man will drink poison just because it is served in a tribal cup. I am surely winning my polling unit for Obi*
In this tweet, the phrase, 'any member of my family that vote Tinubu will be eternally cursed' implies retributive judgment, inferring that voting for Peter Obi is a spiritual assignment and anyone of his family members who does not engage in this spiritual assignment will be eternally damned. The phrase 'eternally cursed' connotes an irreversible punishment from God. This tweet suggests that not voting for Peter Obi is spiritually reprehensible. The use of the words, 'no sane

man will drink poison just because it is served in a tribal cup' implies that voting for a candidate, because he is from the same tribe, is spiritually and morally wrong and therefore tantamount to self-destruction.

Theme 5 Transparency/Good Governance

***Tweet 19** – Peter Obi is the only ex gov who reviews contract fee down to the prevailing market reality and save money for the state. The gov's and presidency we have today is rubber stamp. Give them kickbacks and they will approve your contract fee. I heard Gov Dapo Eleyi is known as Mr 10%.*

This tweet emphasises Peter Obi's transparency and effective governance during his tenure. He was broadly recognised as a proponent of effective governance, transparency, and openness. In Nigeria, unscrupulous politicians increase contract values but never decrease them. Obi, however, did not share this. This is the principal reason the youth desire him as president. The author juxtaposes Obi with the governors and the president, concluding that their corruption is such that they would demand kickbacks before approving a contract fee. He asserts that Governor Dapo is exceedingly corrupt, extorting 10% from any contract he signs, earning him the nickname, Mr. 10%. The use of the Yoruba word 'Eleyi' as the surname of the Governor, which is derogatory, shows the author's disrespect for the Governor due to the corruption the author addressed. The *OBIdients* want Peter Obi as president because he symbolised a departure from the traditional establishment. He embodies hope for Nigeria and its citizens. Their key message is: 'A new Nigeria is 'POssible' under Peter Obi.'

Theme – 6 Hate Politics

***Tweet 20** –The days of billboard politics are over. The choice of the people are in their hearts and they will use their thumbs on Election Day.*

This tweet verbalises the frustration regarding the bias and antagonism the *OBIdients* faced in Delta State during the 2023 election campaigns. This tweet was in response to the allegation that the Governor at that time was tearing the campaign posters of Peter Obi while leaving those of his presidential candidate. The phrase, 'the days of billboard politics are over,' is a clear rejection of a campaign strategy that frustrates the voice of the opposition while encouraging large-scale campaigns from their party. The author's assertion that 'the choice of the people is in their hearts' clearly shows that the people's preference is indelibly etched in their hearts rather than on billboards. The other part of the statement, 'they will use their thumbs on election day,' clearly expresses the author's confidence in the ballot system and his belief that power belongs to the electorate.

***Tweet 21** – Na juju de worry them. Will that stop anybody from voting for Obi. They are standing on their heads.*

The author regards the Governor's removing Peter Obi's posters as inconsequential as that would not deter the *OBIdients* from voting for their presidential candidate. The statement, 'na juju de worry them,' indicates that the action of the Governor stems from profound malevolence. Juju is a form of black magic employed by someone possessing malevolent powers to damage others. Nonetheless, it is used here to signify malevolence. Similar to the last author, this author contends

that removing posters will not deter the *OBIdients* from casting their votes for Peter Obi. He ends by stating that the former Governor and his associates are in a precarious position. In Nigerian parlance, 'standing on one's head' signifies doing something unusually or weirdly. Nonetheless, accurately interpreting the word is to do a task swiftly and proficiently.

Tweet 22 – *Peter Obi is in the heart of the people not in the stickers that what they didn't understand.*

The tweet shows the strong relationship between the *OBIdients* and their preferred presidential candidate, Mr Peter Obi. The statement 'Peter Obi is in the heart of the people...' shows that the support of the *OBIdients* for their preferred candidate is based on their deeply held belief and shared thoughts that Peter Obi is the right candidate who will move Nigeria forward, and not on stickers. Again, the phrase, 'not in the stickers' shows the *OBIdients*' commitment to their course and not on posters and stickers. The last clause in the sentence, 'that what they didn't understand' suggests that the opposition has not understood the deep-hearted support of the *OBIdients* for their chosen candidate. This shows that their support for Peter Obi is based on sincerity of purpose and not on symbols like posters and stickers. The author claims their candidate resides in their hearts, rendering him indelible. Posters and billboards may be eliminated, however, their candidate's preference endures in their hearts.

Tweet 23 – *Even after Okowa use state money do big big billboards for him sef n atiku na small stickers de hunt am...but e allowed APC paint a complete plaza with their candidates.....Isi adiro ya nma.*

The tweet appraises political partiality in election campaigns, especially as allegedly seen in EFG's elimination of little posters of Obi off vehicles. Simultaneously, he had a whole building adorned with his portrait and that of Atiku. The phrase, 'na small stickers dey hunt am' suggests that EFG feels intimidated by little things like stickers and posters. The tweet contrasts Obi's small stickers to EFG's 'big big billboards', which signifies his liberty to 'paint a complete plaza with their candidates' portrait. The tweet concludes with the sentence in Igbo, 'isi adiro ya nma signifying that EFG did not conduct himself appropriately, or in Nigerian English, 'his head is not correct.' This author shows that he is bilingual by writing both English and Igbo.

Theme – 7 Political Killing

Tweet 24 – *I condemn these heinous acts in the strongest possible terms. Such acts violate our spirit of security, civility and the recently signed Peace Accord. Federal and State security agencies must work assiduously to uncover those behind this killing.*

Tweet 25 – *I am deeply disturbed by the evidently targeted killing of the Labour Party State House of Assembly Candidate for Onuimo LGA in Imo State, Hon. Christopher Eleghu at his home. His house and cars were reportedly set ablaze.*

These two tweets highlight the issue of political assassination in electoral campaigns and call for its redress. In tweet 24, the author, Peter Obi, condemns in strong terms the killing of a politician, describing it as a 'heinous' crime, stating that 'such violates the spirit of security, civility, and the recently signed peace accord'. The phrase, 'Federal and State security agencies must work assiduously to uncover those behind this killing' is a call to unravel the perpetrators of the crime.

The formal tone and the language of the tweet differentiate this tweet from the rest of the tweets and therefore show the author as one who is in a position of a leader who empathises with his people.

Tweet 25 addresses the killing of a particular politician, Hon Christopher Eleghu. The author condemns the killing in no uncertain terms. The last sentence of the tweet, 'his house and cars were reportedly set ablaze,' expresses the gruesomeness of the killing. The phrase, 'deeply disturbed,' shows a strong connection between the author and the people he would have led had he won the election. These two tweets portray the author as a responsible, responsive leader and a protector of democratic values.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The principal objective of this study was to examine the prevailing themes in online political campaigns, using the *OBIdient* campaign discourse as a case study. Other ancillary themes were: to examine how the *OBIdient* campaign discourse served as a political protest among the Youth and to examine how the political discourse positioned the Youth as agents of change, thereby mobilising them to take action. This paper addresses the necessity for more investigation into the discourse of the *OBIdient* movement campaign during the 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria. Upon analysing the data extracted from the X post, the researchers observed the following: The predominant themes encompass persuasion (the primary theme of the *OBIdient* movement)- one tweet; adoration – six tweets; appreciation – one tweet; religion/focus – ten tweets; transparency/good governance – one tweet; hate politics – four tweets; and political murder – two tweets. The *OBIdient* movement serves as a clarion cry for Nigerian youth to mobilise and take action. They have endured hardship due to those who refuse to relinquish power. The movement constitutes a kind of political protest. Peter Obi, the pivotal personality of this movement/political protest, conveys a singular message: 'take back your country.' It is YOUR FUTURE that they are toying with,' expresses the youths' frustration and urges them to mobilise and take action. The author emphasised the words YOUR FUTURE, underscoring the future of Nigeria's youth. The theme contained a singular principal tweet. Overall, despite the theme of religion being mentioned most frequently in the tweets (ten instances), followed by the theme of commendation (six instances), the researchers determined that the theme of persuasion/empowerment was the most predominant. This is because that singular message from Peter Obi, 'take back your country...' ignited passion in the hearts of the youth and motivated them to take action. All other themes in the tweets are centred around this theme.

Disclosure Statement

The authors have no conflict of interest.

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